

Data Transfer Configurations

Data transfer is an integral part of device integration. The device integration protocol generally enables the remote access and transfer of data. Both these can be set up separately, with neither relying on the other.

There are two approaches for the data transfer configurations,

- Automatic data transfer
- Manual transfer

While the manual transfer refers to manually collecting, generally using a USB storage device, there are several approaches for the automatic transfer as follows,

- Transferring data through the **email provider**
- **EFW (ELN File Watcher)** running as a program
- **PowerShell script** running as a background service
- **Macro**

In this part, we mostly discuss the configurations required to run EFW (ELN File Watcher) as a program to collect the data automatically. Initially, we have to generate an EFW exe file with custom input fields specifying the source, and destination along with other configuration data. We can generate the EFW instances from the EFW builder. It is a server-side application that securely generates EFW instances. These instances can then be installed on the target system in just a few steps. In addition, this server provides a data storage unit with an interface to receive data from your target systems.

Note: Please [contact us](#) if you need the service of the EFW builder.

The rest of the configurations are as follows,

- Login to the EFW builder
- Create a new EFW executable file with all necessary inputs

Name:	<input type="text"/>
Unique name of the EFW instance. This name cannot be changed!	
User:	<input type="text"/>
WebDAV User	
Password:	<input type="password"/>
WebDAV Password	
Src:	<input type="text"/>
Source directory to be watched.	
Dst:	<input type="text"/>
WebDAV destination URL. If the destination is on the lsd, the URL should be as follows: https://os-webdav.lsd.kit.edu/[OE]/[inst]/projects/[PROJECTNAME]/ [OE]-Organisationseinheit, z.B. kit. [inst]-Institut-Name, z.B. ioc, scc, ikp, imk-asf etc. [USERNAME]-User-Name z.B. xy1234, bs_abcd etc. [PROJECTNAME]-Projekt-Name	
Type:	<input type="text" value="-----"/>
Type must be 'file', 'folder' or 'zip'. The 'file' option means that each file is handled individually, the 'folder' option means that entire folders are transmitted only when all files in them are ready. The option 'zip' sends a folder zipped, only when all files in a folder are ready.	
Duration:	<input type="text" value="300"/>
Duration in seconds, i.e., how long a file must not be changed before sent. (default 300 sec.)	
System architecture:	<input type="text" value="Windows i386"/>
Your computer architecture : either 64 bit or 32 bit (i386)	
<input type="button" value="Submit"/>	

- Download the executable file
- (Optional) Copy the efw.exe into *C:\Program Files\file_exporter*
- Create a Scheduled Task to trigger at startup
 - Copy the [file_exporter_task.vbs](#) into the startup directory. You can also download the file, task_example.vbs from here
 - Hint: Windows Key + R to open run and type shell:startup. This will open the startup directory
 - If you are using another location to keep the exe file, replace the full path of the executable file in the scheduler script.
- After restarting the computer, check from Task Manager if the scheduled task is created and the application process is running

Points to note:

- Make sure the task scheduler is pointing to the correct exe file in the correct location
- After editing the scheduling script, the computer needs to be restarted